

***In vitro* antioxidative property of polyphenols present in two common aquatic leafy vegetables**

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Abstract : *Enydra fluctuans* Lour. (Hinche or helencha) and *Ipomea aquatica* Forssk. (Kalmisak) are traditionally consumed as leafy vegetables by the Indians. But little is known about its potential as sources of antioxidants. The 80% methanol extraction of these two vegetables showed the polyphenol content of 30.7 and 18.42 mg per g of dry matter. Both the extracts have shown reducing activity, DPPH radical scavenging activity and prolonged ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging activity. The result of the study indicates that the above vegetables are rich in active polyphenolic antioxidants, which are very much important from nutritional point of view.

Keywords : *Enydra fluctuans*, *Ipomea aquatica*, polyphenol, antioxidant.

Introduction

Antioxidant compounds in plants for example tocopherols, carotenoids and other phenolic compounds are effective in the protection against oxidative damage¹. Oxidative stress – the consequence of an imbalance of prooxidants and antioxidants in an organism, is rapidly gaining recognition as a key phenomenon in the chronic diseases like CVDs, hypertension, diabetes mellitus and some forms of cancer. Diet consisting of vegetables and fruits play a major role to decrease the oxidative stress. Polyphenols, the natural phytochemicals, are the potent antioxidants in the plant food². Their amount in the diet is 10 times higher than vitamin C and 100 times higher than vitamin D or carotenoid^{3,4}. These natural antioxidants function as free radical scavengers, chain breaking antioxidants, metal chelators, reducing agents, oxidative enzyme inhibitors and quenchers of singlet oxygen⁵.

Enydra fluctuans Lour. (Hinche or helencha) and *Ipomea aquatica* Forssk. (Kalmisak) are commonly used as leafy vegetables throughout South West Bengal as both are abundant in the vast water bodies of Bengal. Both *Enydra* and *Ipomea* are medicinally very important. The leaves of *Enydra* are used as laxative, used to cure inflammation, leucoderma, bronchitis, biliousness and small

pox. It is also useful in skin diseases, liver complaints, gonorrhoea and dyspepsia. The juice is taken in empty stomach as anti dysenteric, decoction with black pepper and is used to cure diabetes⁶.

The whole plant of *Ipomea* is used as antihelmintic, useful in liver complaints, to regain viability after delivery, juice is applied to leprotic wounds, juice of fresh flowers is given as drop in eye diseases⁶.

All the reports have addressed the beneficial effects of these two very important medicinal herbs without addressing the polyphenol content and their antioxidative effect. In the present study our objective is to extract the polyphenolic compounds and evaluate the antioxidative efficiency of the extracts by various *in vitro* methods.

Results and discussion

Polyphenolic components from two leafy vegetables are extracted with 80% methanol, 80% ethanol and water and their polyphenol content as gallic acid equivalent is presented in Table 1. In both the leafy vegetables the polyphenols are best extracted with 80% methanol, followed by ethanol and water. In our previous study⁷ and by Kotamballi *et al.*⁸, the highest yield of phenolic

Fig. 1. Reducing activity of the leafy vegetable extracts.

compounds have been observed during extraction from natural sources in methanol than in ethanol and water. *Enydra* and *Ipomea* contains 30.7 and 18.42 mg/g of polyphenols as gallic acid equivalent respectively. So 80% methanol has been used as extraction medium of both *Enydra* and *Ipomea* polyphenolic compounds and their *in vitro* antioxidative activities are determined.

Table 1. Total polyphenol content of *Enydra fluctuans* and *Ipomea aquatica* using different solvents

Leafy vegetable	Polyphenol content (mg of gallic acid equivalents/g of dry matter)		
	80% Methanol	80% Ethanol	Water
<i>Enydra fluctuans</i>	30.7	13.25	17.54
<i>Ipomea aquatica</i>	18.42	6.79	5.026

Reducing activity : Fig. 1 shows the reducing power of methanolic extracts of the leafy vegetables and ascorbic acid which increases with the increasing concentration from 50–250 µg/g. Reducing power of the leafy vegetables followed the order *Enydra* > *Ipomea*. The reducing power of ascorbic acid was higher than the test samples.

DPPH radical scavenging activity : Free radical scavenging potential of *Enydra* and *Ipomea* at different concentration were tested by DPPH method and results are shown in Fig. 2. Antioxidants in the extracts react with DPPH which is a stable free radical and convert it to 1,1-diphenyl-2-picryl hydrazine. The degree of discoloration indicates the scavenging potentials of the antioxidant extracts. At 20, 50 and 100 ppm concentration of 80% methanolic extract of *Enydra* exhibit 40, 53 and 70% radical scavenging activity while *Ipomea* at similar

Fig. 2. DPPH radical scavenging activity of the leafy vegetable extracts.

concentration exhibited 2, 14 and 17% activity respectively. In both the cases the activity increases with the increasing concentration of the extracts. The activity of the extracts is attributed to their hydrogen donating ability.

ABTS^{•+} radical cation scavenging activity : ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging property reflects the ability of an antioxidant species to donate electron and hydrogen atom to inactivate these radical species. Both the test samples exhibited free radical scavenging activity against free radical ABTS^{•+} cation. The EC₅₀ concentration required to quench 50% of the ABTS^{•+} cation is 0.15, 0.4 and 0.025 mg/mL for *Enydra* and *Ipomea* extracts and ascorbic acid respectively. Concentration of *Ipomea* required to quench 50% of the stable free radical was higher than *Enydra*. Results illustrate that *Enydra* extract has much higher radical scavenging activity compared to *Ipomea*. However the duration of the antioxidant activity for both the extracts occurred over longer duration of time compared to the shorter reaction time for L ascorbic acid. Slow reacting compounds used in the present study are hypothesized to have more complex reaction mechanism involving one or more secondary reactions in the quenching of ABTS^{•+} free radical.

In summary, methanol extract of both *Enydra* and *Ipomea* exhibit strong reducing power, significant DPPH radical scavenging activity and prolonged ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging property. The prolonged period of antioxidant activity of the extracts may be beneficial in the application of extended product shelf life.

Experimental

Both *Enydra fluctuans* (Hinche sak) and *Ipomea aquatica* (Kalmi sak) was purchased from the local market. The vegetables were dried in a vacuum oven at 50 ± 2 °C and finely powdered. The powder was weighed, homogenized and extracted with various solvents at room temperature and filtered. The residue was re-extracted till the filtrate was colorless. The extracts were pooled and evaporated in a rotary evaporator till free of solvent. The polyphenols obtained were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. The content of total polyphenol was estimated using Folin Ciocalteu reagent as described by Matthaues⁹. Antioxidant activity was assessed by DPPH free radical scavenging activity¹⁰. ABTS^{•+} radical scavenging activity¹¹ and reducing power¹² of the extracts were measured by standard methods.

Ascorbic acid, trichloroacetic acid (TCA), ferric chloride (anhydrous) was supplied by E. Merck, India Limited. ABTS and DPPH from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Company, USA; potassium persulfate, Folin Ciocalteu's phenol reagent, gallic acid, potassium ferricyanide, ethyldiene diamine tetra acetic acid disodium salt (EDTA) were purchased from SRL (Sisco Research Laboratory, India). All the experiments were performed by using double distilled water. The absorbance was measured using

Shimadzu (1601A) UV-Vis spectrophotometer. All the results were expressed as an average of three determinations.

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